

Stress Monitoring in the Era of AI Boom - Where Should We Begin?

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Abstract

This Systematic Literature Review (SLR) explores the growing convergence of social sciences, medical sciences, and computer engineering in the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled multimodal stress monitoring systems. We aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of AI-enabled stress monitoring and identify key areas requiring further research and development. Our analyses reveal a fundamental gap in current literature: many studies lack a clear theoretical definition of stress and a standardized methodological design to measure the multifaceted nature of stress. Although our findings highlight a popular method of integrating multimodal data including self-evaluations, physiological signals, behavioral reactions, and responses to environmental stressors, the data sources are often inconsistent and only partially integrated due to personal, contextual, and technical constraints. Moving beyond current focus on maximizing the technical challenges, this review also identifies other key areas, i.e., improving model's accuracy, realizing real-world usability, enhancing data quality, safeguarding ethical use of data, and establishing user trust that require future research to develop more rigorously.

CCS Concepts

• **Social and professional topics** → *User characteristics*; • **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**.

Keywords

Stress, emotions, wearable, AI, mental health, eHealth

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1 Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), stress is a significant public health concern with profound impacts on physical and mental well-being, and it has traditionally been challenging to measure objectively and consistently across contexts and populations [78]. Feeling under stress is a common experience that everyone face at least once in their life time. In fact, stress can serve as a motivator for people to accomplish more [74] but also have negative effects on decision-making and interpersonal relationships if stress prolonged and maintained at high-intensity level without proper treatments [1].

Thanks to the rapid advancement of AI technologies, it has transformed different aspects of general and mental healthcare [14, 17, 64]. Recently, an increasing integration of AI applications into stress detection systems can be found in research [21, 27, 39, 41, 71, 76]. The combination of using different modalities of data, including self-reports, physiological signals, behavioral patterns, and environmental stressors, and integrating Machine Learning (ML) techniques to analyze human stress has made the AI-enabled stress monitoring highly valuable to advance mental healthcare [34, 40]. Benefits are such as easier access to mental health resources and lower healthcare costs [32, 47].

It is evident that the integration of AI into stress monitoring has created new opportunities for early detection and intervention in real-world environments [71, 76]. Therefore, this SLR examines how stress is conceptualized and measured in contemporary AI-enabled applications while identifying the critical challenges facing this evolving field.

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This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the methodology used in this study including objectives, research questions, and methods. Section 3 demonstrates our findings, and a comprehensive discussion is presented in Section 4.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Questions

This research paper addresses two fundamental questions at the intersection of AI and stress monitoring:

RQ1: How is stress defined and measured in the most current literature?

RQ2: What are prominent challenges within the field?

Answering these questions will aid in gaining a deeper understanding of the most current stress research using AI and ML for stress monitoring via smart wearables. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of AI-enabled stress monitoring and identify key areas requiring further research and development.

2.2 Review Strategy

Review Protocol. The structure of this review protocol is guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. Initially, we searched scientific databases: Scopus, Web of Science, and Medline-PubMed, using combinations of keywords. The query searched on Scopus is the following:

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((stress OR anxi* OR depress* OR ((mental OR emotional) AND stress)) AND (detection OR recognition OR prediction OR classification OR monitoring) AND (AI OR "artificial intelligence" OR ml OR "machine learning" OR measurement OR definition OR (data AND (analysis OR processing) OR "feature extraction" OR "affective computing")) AND (smart* OR wearable* OR (smart AND (device* OR technolog* OR ring* OR shoe* OR cloth* OR glass* OR headset* OR watch*))))
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The selection criteria applied were prioritized to: (1) terms of three concepts appearing in the title, abstract, or keywords, (2) published between 2018 and 2024, (3) English-only articles.

Study Selection And Assessment of the Quality of the Studies. A broad interdisciplinary criterion was considered in the fields of Social Sciences, Psychology, Computer Science, Engineering, and Medicine. Reasons to select different fields are as following:

- For conceptual frameworks and clinical insights, we included studies from psychology and social science.
- For physiological measures and health impacts, medical and behavioral sciences research is included.
- For data analytic and technological approaches to stress monitoring, articles from computer science and engineering involving affective computing are included.

The primary search results were Scopus (1717), Web of Science (898), and PubMed (866). A total of 716 duplicates were identified and removed. Articles (103) that focus on stress in non-human participants (e.g. water stress of power plants, agriculture) and do not have open access were primarily excluded. Six stages of screening took place, see PRISMA flow chart in Figure 1. The initial search was broad because we wanted to include all relevant studies that examined stress, especially given the fact that stress, anxiety and depression sharing overlapping symptoms [26, 75, 81]. However,

Figure 1: Articles screening methodology.

according to American Psychiatric Association (APA) [61], anxiety and depression are classified as mental disorders, and the WHO [77] refers stress as a response to external challenges but a disorder. We made a clear conceptual distinction between the three and maintained our focus specifically on stress. Therefore, we excluded studies that primarily centered on anxiety, depression, or other diagnosable mental disorders. The final selection after the refinement is of 21 papers, which we then analyzed from a holistic perspective to develop a clearer and more comprehensive understanding of how stress is conceptualized in different contexts in the most current literature.

3 Results

3.1 RQ1 – Definitions and Measurements of Stress

3.1.1 Definitions of Stress. Because stress is a complex human response, various definitions have emerged across different disciplines aiming to clarify this complex nature of human phenomenon for broader public comprehension.

From affective computing and engineering perspectives, stress is often defined as an arousal state that can be detected by AI and technological systems [4]. Stress is measured via the combination of physiological and behavioral features in computational contexts via the use of machine learning techniques. The technology is used to collect and analyze physiological and physical manifestation of one's affective state to determine a person's current emotional

state [28]. A comprehensive approaches suggested by [5] proposing exploration of stress through connections between health outcomes and the intensity and duration of stress. In a comprehensive review of the existing literature, the definitions and measurements of stress can be categorized into two main scientific perspectives: (a) psychology and social science, (b) medical and behavioral science.

(a) Psychology Perspectives. Seven studies adopted a psychological lens to define stress. Among them, three [2, 11, 12] explicitly referenced the APA definition [3], which characterizes stress as “a normal reaction to everyday pressures, but which can become unhealthy when it disrupts day-to-day functioning,” further noting that stress affects “nearly every system of the body, influencing how people feel and behave”. The remaining four studies offered alternative psychological interpretations. One study defined stress as a personal experience triggered by occupational demands [56]; two studies emphasized individual coping mechanisms and the variability in stress response [33, 69]; and one study framed stress as a mood state, reflecting the complex, bidirectional relationship between an individual and their environment, capable of producing both positive and negative outcomes [58].

(b) Medicine and Behavioral Sciences Perspectives. Five studies defined stress from a medical or behavioral standpoint. Two studies [7, 67] drew from historical definitions established by Hans Selye, a Hungarian-Canadian endocrinologist who, in 1936, introduced stress as a physiological and psychological reaction to environmental demands, which often involves emotional or physical discomfort and disruptions to homeostasis [59]. In this tradition, stress is viewed as an arousal state, which is closely intertwined with psychological and physiological responses. Additionally, one study referenced Walter Cannon’s early 20th-century theory of the “fight-or-flight” response, which conceptualized stress as the activation of the sympathetic nervous system in response to perceived threats [13]. The remaining three studies [9, 22, 50] described stress as the body’s effort to restore internal equilibrium when disrupted by external or internal stimuli.

3.1.2 Multimodal Measurements of Stress. Due to the multifaceted nature of stress, measuring stress accurately has been seem a challenging task. Researchers have developed a wide array of tools to measure different modalities of stress signals. In terms of human emotions, according to [35], the techniques are mainly categorized into three major aspects: questionnaires, physical, and physiological signals. However, our SLR reveals that apart from those three classifying techniques, environmental factors were also integrated to examine the indirect effects on stress. Therefore, building on [35], we categorize responses to stress-related emotions measured from four categories: Self-evaluation (SLF), Physiological Signals (PHYS), Behavioral Reactions (BHV), and Environmental Factors (ENVM), which are illustrated in Figure 2.

SLF includes questionnaires and surveys, which are used to estimate individuals’ perceived emotional states. Several commonly used scales include the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) [15], Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) [63], Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ) [36], Self Assessment Manikin (SAM) [37], and Rating Scale Mental Effort (RSEM) [80], which use questionnaires to estimate stress. Other scales include Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) for measuring sleep quality [8], UCLA Loneliness Scale (UCLA-LS) [54]

for measuring one’s subjective feeling of loneliness, and Flourishing Scale (FS) [19] that measures the subjective feeling of psychological well-being. Oldenburg Burnout Inventory Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OBI) [18], Profile of Mood States (POMS) [46], and the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [29] are often used to examine job stress.

The PHYS modality captures changes in the body’s signals that directly respond to stress-related emotions. Objective measures include cardiovascular parameters [25] (e.g., Heart Rate (HR), Heart Rate Variability (HRV), Blood Volume Pulse (BVP), Respiration (RSP) rate), electrodermal activity [65] (e.g., Electrodermal Activity (EDA), Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), Skin Temperature (SKT), Skin Conductance Response (SCR), and Skin Conductance Level (SCL)), increasing respiration [49], and other bodily movements [16](e.g., sleep quality, physical activities, and movement patterns, which can be measured by Accelerometer (ACC)). Our findings reveal that Electrodermal and cardiovascular activities are most prevalent among physiological sensors, which further confirm their robustness as a biomarker of stress, see Figure 2.

BHV refers to behavioral patterns. When experiencing stress, features such as sleep [51], physical activity [67], and phone usage [70] can provide valuable insights into linking behavioral patterns to stress, despite the complexity involved in associating behavioral markers with mental health conditions [23, 45]. Among all included studies, 10 explored behavioral patterns combining other modalities to identify stress. While [56, 58, 69] investigated one’s frequent and habitual usage of technological devices, others [7, 23, 67, 70] exclusively investigated ones’ physical activity patterns. Only [2, 45, 57] investigated both.

ENVM includes weather conditions, illuminance, noise, and traffic. The indirect measures of the changes to one’s contextual information (e.g., geographical location, environment, and social life) can reveal the relationship between perceived stress and physiological stress [7, 48]. For instance, social isolation, job-specific stressors, and location. Recent studies have proven that changes in environment such as day light duration and weather conditions

Figure 2: Main types of measuring modalities in stress responses.

are a known stressor for some individuals with seasonal affective disorder [72]. Some other environmental stressors such as increased traffic, noisy city were also demonstrated to have indirect stress impact on some individuals [30, 44]. We found only two [7, 57] studies in this review considered environmental stressors having influence on one's experience to stress.

How multimodal measurements are used and data collected via different wearables are summarized in detail in Table 1, and the frequent utilization of the individual metric is shown in Figure 3.

3.2 RQ2 – Identified Challenges

Figure 4 demonstrates the distribution of different types of challenges identified within the included studies. Five major aspects of challenges are identified and they are described in the following.

[ML Problem.] The majority of the included studies employed binary Classification (C) models (76%) to distinguish between stress and non-stress states. A smaller number of studies (24%) implemented 3-class classification approach, categorizing stress into low, medium, and high level. Among all, only 24% of studies emphasize on Prediction (P). However, there was a notable absence of models capable of capturing more nuanced or contextualized types of stress.

[Limited Number of Stress Classes.] A substantial amount of the studies (76%) focused exclusively on stress classification, highlighting the dominance of classification tasks in the current research agenda. In contrast, only 24% of the studies investigated predictive modeling approaches aimed at forecasting stress before it manifests. This distribution difference in current research suggests a strong emphasis on reactive, rather than proactive, stress monitoring strategies.

[Technical Aspects.] Three sub-domains were categorized: model architecture, data processing, and hardware-specific constraints.

- Model **architecture** challenges primarily involved issues with generalizability, model reliability, and prediction accuracy, which make these systems difficult to implement in real-world settings [9, 10, 22, 23, 45, 50, 67–70, 73].
- **Data processing** limitations include restricted use of classification algorithms and a narrow range of feature extraction techniques. This constrained the models' ability to capture diverse and informative signals from multimodal data sources [9, 11, 22, 23, 33, 55, 68, 69, 73].
- **Hardware-specific** issues were particularly evident in studies using multiple wearables, for example in [2]. They encountered a trade-off between energy consumption and predictive performance, affecting the feasibility of continuous stress monitoring.

[Methodological Design.] Two critical aspects were identified: context specificity and data collection quality.

- In terms of **context specificity**, many studies lacked fine-grained contextual sensing, particularly in real-life environments. This limited the clear validity of the collected data and model outputs [7, 53].
- **Data collection** challenges included low-quality data, limited sample size, presence of noise, sensor malfunction, and

data transmission inefficiencies, all compromising the robustness and accuracy of stress detection models [2, 10–12, 45, 50, 56–58, 67, 70].

[Individualized Factors.] Several studies highlighted the limited attention paid to individual differences, which are **user related** issues. There was a general lack of understanding in individual's stress triggers and unique coping mechanisms [2, 7, 12, 33, 53, 55–58, 68, 69].

4 Discussion

4.1 Current State of Stress Definitions and Measurements

Our findings highlight a growing trend toward the convergence of social sciences, medical sciences, and computer engineering in addressing crucial challenges of mental healthcare. It reflects a broader recognition that stress is not solely a psychological experience, a physiological reaction, or a behavioral pattern, but a multifaceted construct that must be approached holistically [78]. However, we observed a significant shortcoming in current literature investigating AI-enabled stress monitoring: a lack of theoretical grounding in how stress is defined at the start of the research process. In our view, fundamental concepts and definitions shape what researchers choose to measure, which data they prioritize, how they label datasets and interpret results.

In addition, our analyses reveal an important development in the increasing emphasis on integrating multimodal data sources, including self-reports, physiological biomarkers, behavioral patterns, and environmental factors. This multimodal approach aligns with the multidimensional nature of stress. We found research studies varying in choosing how to use multimodal sources, either in combination or independently. In many studies, data sources are used independently or only partially integrated. Reasons include limited usability of certain wearable technology in daily environment [2, 22], data collection constraints in certain contexts [7, 53], or suffering from a limited size of participant [2, 9–12, 50, 53, 55, 68]. We can almost certainly say that analyzing the correlations between different modalities is the way to ensure stress detection more "accurate" or "effective", since a single modal cannot be definitive without incorporating other modality for the measurement [7, 45, 56, 57]. Researchers collect and process these data via ML techniques in order to find the next "best" or "accurate" model to detect stress. Incorporating multimodal approaches to access stress instead of focusing on one particular method has been proved to bring great potential and advantages to a more holistic understanding of stress [7, 20].

However, while a significant recognition on integrating multimodal information is present in current literature, the real-world applications in synchronizing multimodal stress data remain limited. In particular, we found very little emphasis on environmental stressors, such as noise, lighting, traffic, or crowding space, which can have impact on daily stress levels [7].

It is worthy to mention that in our recent proof-of-concept study [41], we explored the practicality of using multimodal data for stress prediction. We focused on the role of individual geographical movement data as an exploratory modality for stress mapping. We

Table 1: Summary of stress definitions and measurements from the included studies. The table is sorted by year.

Refs, Year	Category	Stress Definition Used in the Study	Data Collection	Subjects	Devices	Modality	ML Problem, Classes
[10] 2023	n/a	n/a	Debates on a social issue	14	Empatica E4	SLF (PSS), PHY (BVP, EDA, ACC)	C, 2
[73] 2023	n/a	n/a	High-stakes examination week	83	Empatica E4	SLF (EMA, PHY (HR,EDA)	C, 2
[55] 2023	n/a	n/a	Individuals diagnosed with Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD) and undergoing treatment	11	Empatica E4	SLF (EMA, PHY (BVP, HR, EDA, SKT, ACC)	C, 2
[56] 2023	PSY	Stress is a personal experience caused by demands. Here focuses on job stress to its impact on the performance and success of organizations [6], [66].	Employees' perception of job stress and their recognized behavior patterns	57	FitBit, desktop screen, keyboard, mouse	SLF (customized), PHY (HR, ACC), BEH (keyboard, mouse, windows)	C, 3
[53] 2023	n/a	n/a	Workers performing 4 tasks including Tier social stress test, mental arithmetic stress tests, stroop color word inference test, math and memory tests.	20	ShimmerGSR back strap, Logitech C920 HD Pro webcam	SLF (customized), PHY (HR, HRV, IBI, RRI, EDA, eye blinks)	C, 2
[9] 2023	MED	An organism's natural reaction to an intrinsic or extrinsic situation, whether it be favourable or unfavourable, physical or mental, is known as stress [79]. It is the body's method of coping with an oppressive or negative situation and constantly works to restore the body to its normal balance [62].	Individuals performing 5 tasks including construct lego objects, math counting, CV presentation	29	Empatica E4	PHY (BVP, HRV, Peak-to-Peak Intervals (PPI), SCR, EDA, SKT, ACC)	C, 2
[58] 2023	PSY	Stress is the mood of pressure and tension that a person feels. Stress is a multidimensional phenomenon that focuses on the dynamic relationship, bringing both positive and negative outcomes, between person and environment.	Detect stress through behavioral data	110	Smartphone	SLF (customized), PHY (HR, ACC), BEH (frequency of touch screen)	C, 2
[67] 2022	MED	Stress is defined by Selye [60] as "the non-specific response of the body to any demand for change.	Stress detection with context	827	Imec's chillband, smartphone, GoPro camera	SLF(customized), PHY (EDA, SKT, ACC), BEH (sitting, standing, walking, lying down, running, sleeping)	C, 3
[50] 2022	MED	The human body responds to stressful situations by activating the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenocortical axis and sympathetic-adrenomedullary axis. Referred to the effect of psychological stress on the body's physiological response [42].	Stressed and non-stressed state in older adults	19	Shimmer 3 GSR+	PHY (BVP, EDA, saliva)	C, 2
[7] 2022	MED	Stress is a complex physiological phenomenon and the term was first employed by Hans Selye [59] to describe the bodily reactions of mice to non-specific noxious agents (e.g., cold exposure, acute injury, excessive exercise, drugs).	A longitudinal study with salaried information workers	597	Garmin Vivomart 3, Zephyr chest strap, Bluetooth Beacons, key-fob, smartphone	SLF (STAI), PHY (HR, HRV), BEH (motion, step count, physical activity), ENVM (weather, sunrise, sunset, time of day, temperature, humidity, wind)	P, 2
[22] 2022	MED	Stress is the body's response to environmental threats, triggering what is known as the fight or flight response [26].	Stress experiment induced via an air horn sound	35	Empatica E4	PHY (EDA, SKT)	C, 2
[45] 2021	n/a	n/a	Examining work-related stress using features derived from sensors in smartphones on employees of two enterprises	30	Samsung Galaxy S3 mini 32 GB smartphone	SLF (OBI and POMS), PHY (ACC), BEH (physical activity, location, microphone, calls, SMS, App usage)	P, 3
[23] 2021	n/a	n/a	Context-aware speech stress detection in hospital workers	212	Fitbit charge 2 wristband, Unihertz Jelly Pro smartphone, an OMSignal smartshirt/bra	SLF (customized), PHY (HR, HRV), BEH (audio-pitch, intensity, voicing, location)	C, 2
[68] 2021	n/a	n/a	Predicting stressful and non-stressful moments in everyday settings	14	Samsung sport gear smartwatches, smartphone	SLF (EMA), PHY (HR, HRV)	P, 2
[70] 2020	n/a	n/a	Predicting stress on college students	45	Smartphone	SLF (PHQ-9, PSS, PSQI UCLA-LS, FS), BEH (mobility patterns, Global Positioning System (GPS), physical activity inferences, conversation)	P, 2
[69] 2020	PSY	Stress is defined as an imbalance between external forces or loads and individual's possibilities to cope with or resist those external forces [38].	Office workers' stress on their daily activities.	74	Polar M600 smartwatches, Android smartphone	SLF (EMA), PHY (HR, Inter-beat (RR) Intervals (RRI), Inter-Beat Intervals (IBI), ACC), BEH (Phone usage, screen status, App usage)	P, 2
[33] 2020	MED	Used Maslach and Jackson's [43] definition of burnout as "a syndrome of emotional exhaustion and cynicism".	Detection of stress on physicians in the emergency department.	8	Empatica E4	SLF (customized), PHY (HR, EDA, SKT, ACC)	C, 2
[12] 2020	n/a	n/a	Teachers participated in tasks: reading magazines, giving a lecture, and taking an exam	32	Samsung Gear S & Gear S2, Empatica E4	SLF (NASA-TLX), PHY (RRI, IBI, EDA, SKT, SCL, SCR, ACC)	C, 3
[11] 2019	PSY	Used American Psychological Association's definition of psychological stress as an emotional response to an external trigger and has two types: acute and chronic [52]	Summer camp participants solving challenges within limited time in an algorithmic programming contest.	21	Samsung Gear S1, S2, S3 smartwatches, Empatica E4	SLF (NASA-TLX), PHY (RRI, IBI, EDA, SKT, SCL, SCR, ACC)	C, 3
[57] 2018	n/a	n/a	College students' self-reported stress and mental health status monitoring	201	Q-sensor, Motion Logger wrist-worn wearables, Android smartphone	SLF (customized), BEH (sleeping and wake patterns, App usage, calls, SMS), ENVM (ambient light exposure, humidity)	C, 2
[2] 2018	n/a	The International Labor Organization defines stress as the harmful physical and emotional response caused by insufficient perceived resources and abilities of individuals to cope with the perceived demands, and is determined by work organization, work design and labor relations [31]	Simulating smart offices in real work setting to predict occupational stress under different workloads	25	A computer log pressing button, a Kinect SDK face reader	SLF (SAM, RSEM, NASA-TLX), BEH (computer usage pattern, facial expressions, posture)	C, 2

Figure 3: Distribution of different measuring modalities of stress.

Figure 4: Challenges identified within the included studies.

found that analyzing one's contextual information via GPS holds potential for predicting or flagging one's real-time response to a stressful situation. For instance, a person continuously experiencing stress when commuting through a crowded area might benefit from personalized suggestions to reroute, reschedule, or apply a coping strategy that fit an individual's unique preferences or needs to that specific context. Our findings highlighted that personalized and location-based feedback is key to adoption for stress monitoring.

4.2 Gaps in AI-enabled Stress Monitoring and Management

One key observation across the included studies is that the majority of AI-driven stress tools remain focused on detection rather than prediction, which presents a significant obstacle for providing proactive preventive measures to stress [7, 70]. While detecting stress after it occurs may support the understanding of the abnormalities of the biometric data, the ultimate goals (i.e., early identification and proactive support) in stress research are still failed to achieve. In the best scenario, AI systems through continuous monitoring of physiological, behavioral, and contextual signals should be able to anticipate when an individual is beginning to enter a stressed state and offer personalized recommendations for coping stressful events. These coping mechanisms might involve with breathing exercises, going for a forest walk, or encouraging evident-based types of behavioral adjustments [14, 17, 64].

Interestingly, this functionality has begun to appear in consumer-grade devices. For example, some smartwatches (e.g., Garmin smartwatch series or Apple Watch) offer functions such as notifying users when a stress measurement is peaked. However, their clinical validity and reliability of the sensor systems are questionable. From our viewpoint, consumer-grade devices often rely on simplified algorithms and sensors that do not meet medical-grade standards. This raises concerns about measurement accuracy, data security, and the user's inconsistent behavior [23, 45, 69]. For example, a user might forget to charge the device, wear it when engaging in physical activity? Other common concerns including data transmission inefficiencies, missing annotations, and noisy signals may have negative impact on the model's performance and user trust [10, 50, 56, 67]. The aforementioned underscores why AI-enabled stress research is not only technically demanding but also methodologically flawed. Many questions remain unanswered that include model generalizability, real-world usability, and the system's practicality in real-world applications when facing imbalanced data conditions.

Beyond the technical and methodological challenges, we must also address the ethical implications, particularly those related to data privacy and transparency. For instance, the physiological responses, location history, and communication patterns reveal detailed information of a person. According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [24], such intimate data are considered sensitive and must be handled with informed consent, strict data access control, and user accountability. Some critical questions we need to keep in mind are such as: How do we ensure individuals understand what is being collected, how it is interpreted, and who has access to these inferences in order to build user trust? How can we design a system that is doing more good than harm in the aspect of tackling stress?

4.3 Conclusion

To summaries, the integration of innovative technologies, AI, and ML holds a great potential for the development of effective AI-enabled stress monitoring and management systems [14, 34, 64]. Such systems are expected to offer real-time feedback, promoting self-awareness, and delivering personalized stress management techniques that can empower individuals to independently monitor and manage their stress. However, it is important to acknowledge the critical challenges that identified in this SLR. Future research should aim at developing reliable, longitudinal, and ethically-informed systems to support individuals via context-aware and personalized mental well-being monitoring in their natural environment.

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List of abbreviations

ACC	Accelerometer
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APA	American Psychiatric Association
AUD	Alcohol Use Disorder
BHV	Behavioral Reactions
BVP	Blood Volume Pulse
C	Classification
EDA	Electrodermal Activity
EMA	Ecological Momentary Assessment
EMA	Ecological Momentary Assessment
ENVM	Environmental Factors
FS	Flourishing Scale
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSR	Galvanic Skin Response
GSR	Galvanic Skin Response
HR	Heart Rate
HRV	Heart Rate Variability
IBI	Inter-Beat Intervals
ML	Machine Learning
ML	Machine Learning
NASA-TLX	NASA Task Load Index
OBI	Oldenburg Burnout Inventory
P	Prediction
PHQ	Patient Health Questionnaire
PHYS	Physiological Signals
POMS	Profile of Mood States
PPI	Peak-to-Peak Intervals
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PSQI	Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index
PSQI	Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index
PSS	Perceived Stress Scale
RRI	Inter-beat (RR) Intervals
RSEM	Rating Scale Mental Effort
RSP	Respiration
SAM	Self Assessment Manikin
SCL	Skin Conductance Level
SCR	Skin Conductance Response
SKT	Skin Temperature
SKT	Skin Temperature
SLF	Self-evaluation
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
UCLA-LS	UCLA Loneliness Scale
WHO	World Health Organization